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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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CRIMINOLOGIST

(Poem in Acronym)

Criminalistics: The science of crime detections.

Responsible: Professional Criminologist who are responsible in all his/her dealings.

Investigators: Investigators of the Context of all crimes in his/her area of responsibility.

Masterpiece: Experts in his/her professions.

Initiative: Initiative in servant leadership and dynamic behavior.

Noble: Having a high moral and acceptable principle.

Open-mindedness: Accessible, honest, optimistic and receptive.

Loyalty: Loyalty to the law of the Almighty, Strong and self-reliant.

Original: New, fresh and Unique.

Gallant: Brave, fight for truth and just.

Inspirational: Providing or showing creative or spiritual inspiration.

Sensitivity: Act of discernment to the immediate need of the needy.

Tenacity: Resiliency in all trials, obstacles and challenges.